

Potential of rice stubble in spreading tungro in West Bengal, India

P. Tarafder and S. Mukhopadhyay, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani, Nadia, West Bengal, India

An experiment was conducted to determine the potential of rice stubble for spreading tungro virus disease in rice fields. Taichung Native 1 (TN1) seedlings were grown under heavy tungro inoculum pressure, which infected the plants markedly. After harvest clumps of stubble of the infected plants were carefully uprooted. Some intact clumps were placed in pots. The others were chopped, mixed with soil, and placed in pots. The intact stubbles were then tested at 15-day intervals for the presence of the virus.

Test seedlings of TN1 were transplanted into the pots containing the soil-stubble mixture under insect-proof conditions and then tested 10 days later. Freshly emerged *Nephotettix virescens* collected from the rearing chambers were released and kept on the seedlings for several days. The seedlings were then observed for 20 days.

A field experiment was conducted to study the efficiency of stubble as the

Table 1. Transmission of rice tungro virus from Taichung Native 1 (TN1) stubble of different ages. West Bengal, India.

Stubble age at acquisition feeding time (days from harvest)	Time of transmission	Transmission in seedlings (%)
<i>Boro season 1977^a</i>		
15	1st wk, May	20.0
30	3d wk, May	13.3
4s	1st wk, June	13.3
60	3d wk, June	6.6
7s	1st wk, July	6.6
90	3d wk, July	0
105	1st wk, Aug.	0
120	36 wk, Aug.	0
<i>Kharif crop 1978^b</i>		
15	1st wk, Jan.	33.3
30	3d wk, Jan.	26.6
4s	1st wk, Feb.	20.0
60	3d wk, Feb.	13.3
75	1st wk, March	6.6
90	3d wk, March	0
105	1st wk, April	0
120	3d wk, April	0

^aVirus source: infected boro crop harvested in April 1977.

^bVirus source: infected aman crop harvested in Dec. 1977.

virus source in the field. Twenty-five-day-old seedlings of TN1, Jaya, and Ratna

Table 2. Potential of 60-day-old rice stubble to act as the source of tungro virus in the field. 1978 kharif, West Bengal, India.

Variety	Infection (%)
Ratna	2.1
Jaya	4.0
TN1	11.5

were transplanted in 1-m² replicated plots in a randomized block design. One pot of infected stubble was placed at the center of each plot. Each plot was covered with nylon netting on wooden frames, and freshly emerged leafhoppers were released on it. The plants were observed until the booting stage, and the numbers with disease symptoms were recorded (Table 1).

The study confirmed that infected stubble can act as a virus source in the field (Table 2). Stubble can maintain the virus for 75 days in boro. But the efficiency of stubble transmission from boro stubble was lower than that from kharif stubble. The extent of transmission in both cases declined with increasing stubble age.

The Indian Council of Agricultural Research provided financial assistance for this work. □

Soil and crop management

Seed treatment to overcome zinc deficiency in direct-seeded rice

D. B. Mengel and F. E. Wilson, Rice Experiment Station, Louisiana Agricultural Experiment Station (LAES), Crowley, J. E. Sedberry, Jr., Agronomy Department (LAES), Baton Rouge; and F. J. Peterson, Idlewild Experiment Station, LAES, Clinton, Louisiana, USA

Zinc deficiency in seedling rice is common in Louisiana. When recognized, it is usually corrected with a foliar application of Zn-EDTA. But in small seedlings, stands can be reduced severely before farmers recognize the problem and apply zinc.

Seed treatment with Zn-EDTA was evaluated as a means of preventing zinc

deficiency in seedling rice. Field experiments were conducted for 4 years on a Crowley silt loam soil, a Typic Haplaqualf. Soil pH was 7.6 and 0.1 N HCl extractable soil zinc was 0.5 ppm. The zinc was added to the seed by diluting a commercial 6% Zn-EDTA solution with water, adding the diluted

mixture to the seed, and tumbling to ensure thorough mixing. The rates of zinc varied each year — 0.03, 0.05, 0.06, and 0.11 kg Zn/ha were added in 1973 through 1976. The rice was drill sown at 100 kg/ha. Adequate nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium were applied. The plots were mechanically harvested.

Effect of Zn-EDTA seed treatment on the yield of Vista rice, Crowley, Louisiana, USA.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)				Mean
	1973	1974	1975	1976	
No zinc	2.3	2.5	2.3	3.3	2.6
Zinc coated	3.0	4.1	3.3	3.9	3.6
Difference	0.7	1.6	1.0	0.6	1.0
LSD 0.05	0.4	0.7	0.4	0.7	0.3

Yields were corrected to 12% grain moisture.

Coating rice seeds with relatively small amounts of zinc resulted in increased grain yields each year. The mean increase over the 4 years was 1 t/ha, ranging from 0.6 to 1.6 t/ha (see table).

Although yield increases were significant, zinc deficiency symptoms were observed in all plots each year. But the symptoms were less severe and occurred later with zinc seed treatment. The symptoms of zinc deficiency indicate that the seed treatment, although beneficial, did not

supply all the zinc that the plants needed in the Crowley soil. Other zinc sources are being evaluated, along with higher rates of zinc seed coatings, to overcome the deficiency. □

Response of direct-seeded rice to zinc application in Sudan Gezira

George I. Ghobrial, senior rice agronomist, Agricultural Research Corporation, Was Medani, Sudan

Direct-seeded rice in the Sudan Gezira often shows symptoms of zinc deficiency, particularly in early growth stages. Although most symptoms usually disappear soon after continuous flooding begins (5–6 weeks after seeding), the effect of flooding on available zinc in the soil has not been determined. Therefore, to determine the importance of zinc application to rice production (IR298-12-1-1) in the Gezira, an experiment with 5 levels of zinc (0, 2, 4, 6, and 8 kg Zn/ha) was established in 1977 at the Gezira Research Farm. The design was randomized complete block with six replications. At seeding, the zinc,

Effects of zinc level on plant height, grain yield, straw yield, and major components of grain yield of IR298-12-1-1 planted at Gezira Research Station, Sudan.

Zinc level (kg Zn/ha)	Plant ht (cm)	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Straw yield (kg/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	1,000-grain wt (g)
0	83	4,143	6,688	398	75	20.1
2	85	4,333	7,076	387	17	20.2
4	84	4,250	6,688	396	15	20.3
6	85	4,514	7,076	417	77	20.3
8	87	4,662	7,628	398	76	20.3
S.E.	1.17	144	188	13.5	3.2	0.02

as zinc sulfate, was incorporated into the soil (heavy clay with av. pH of 8.5). The effects of zinc level on plant height, straw yield, and major grain yield components were determined.

The experiment showed that Gezira soils are slightly deficient in available zinc (see table). Grain and straw yields increased progressively with level of

applied zinc (P = 0.05). The application of 8 kg Zn/ha increased grain yield by 12% and straw yield by 14%. The increase in grain yield suggests the positive effect on dry matter production of applied zinc, which increased straw yield and grain specific weight. Zinc level had no significant effect on plant height, number of grains per panicle, or number of tillers. □

Production of blue-green algae in the field

S. Kannaiyan, Plant Pathology Laboratory, Paddy Experiment Station, Tirur-602025, Chingleput district, Tamil Nadu, India

Blue-green algae harness solar energy to fix nitrogen. The rice plants use the nitrogen released by the blue-green algae. Thus, a rice field is an efficient nonsymbiotic nitrogen-fixing ecosystem. In submerged rice soils, biological nitrogen fixation is essentially an algal process that contributes 20 to 30 kg N/ha. Mass-scale multiplication of blue-green algae was attempted in a rice field. Soil was well prepared and levelled. The plots (10 × 2 m) were laid out. Superphosphate, lime, carbofuran, and starter culture were applied at three levels (see table).

The water level in the plots was maintained at 10 cm. Superphosphate

and lime were added and mixed well with the water. The plots were inoculated with the starter culture (*Aulosira*, *Anabaena*, *Aphanthece*, *Nostoc*). Finally, carbofuran was applied to control soil insects. The plots were not disturbed.

When daily evaporation was high, the plots were irrigated intermittently. The algae grew rapidly. In about 10 days algae formed a thick mat floating on the water surface. Fifteen days after inoculation the plots were allowed to dry

Mass production of blue-green algae in the field, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Soil-based blue-green algal yield (kg)				Mean algal yield (kg)
	Rep. 1	Rep. 2	Rep. 3	Rep. 4	
Superphosphate : 500 g Lime : 50 g Carbofuran : 100 g Starter culture : 500 g	18.7	19.4	21.2	15.2	18.6
Superphosphate : 1000 g Lime : 100 g Carbofuran : 150 g Starter culture : 1000 g	20.6	18.9	22.1	24.5	21.5
Superphosphate : 1500 g Lime : 150 g Carbofuran : 200 g Starter culture : 1500 g	24.2	25.3	24.6	22.6	24.1